

Synthesis, characterization and application of Mn doped cuprous oxide nanoparticles

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Abstract : Different morphologies of cuprous oxide (Cu_2O) nanoparticles (NPs) were synthesized at higher temperature using thermal decomposition method. The properties of cuprous oxide nanoparticles can be controlled by using different amounts of dopant (Mn^{2+}). The synthesized nanoparticles were characterized by several techniques such as high resolution scanning electron microscopy (HR-SEM), X-ray diffraction pattern (XRD), transmission electron microscopy (TEM), electron diffraction (ED) pattern and energy dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDS). The nanoparticles of Cu_2O and Mn doped Cu_2O were found to have excellent activity for the Micheal addition reaction. The reaction was monitored through GC.

Keywords : Mn doped Cu_2O , catalysis, semiconductor nanoparticles, transition metal, morphology.

Introduction

In chemical sciences, synthesis of nanoparticles is a growing research area due to their interesting properties such as large surface-to-volume ratio, scientific and industrial interests as compared to bulk materials¹. Transition metal oxides have received much attention recently due to their application in electronic, optical, solar energy conservation, catalysis^{2,3}, etc.

Cuprous oxide (Cu_2O) is one of the most important semiconductors with a direct wide band gap of 2.17 eV at room temperature⁴. Cu_2O is a potential candidate among the metal oxide nanoparticles due to its application in catalysis⁵⁻⁷, optical, electrical, and mechanical fields^{8,9}. Copper and copper oxide have received much attention because of its easy preparation method, the non-toxic nature, easy availability and economic importance¹⁰. Physical properties of semiconductor can be changed by doping it with metal ion¹¹. Doping of semiconductor nanomaterials with transition metal ions improve different functional capacities of nanoparticles as compared to undoped counterparts¹². Various metal ions can be used to dope metal oxide nanoparticles. Mn^{2+} is a good dopant for

doping semiconductor nanoparticles¹³. Different methods have been reported for preparing cuprous oxide nanoparticles by hydrothermal¹⁴, microwave irradiation¹⁵, electrochemical deposition¹⁶, wet chemical¹⁷⁻¹⁹ and reverse micellar²⁰ route, but comparatively thermal decomposition method has been found better than others. In thermal decomposition method, one can control size and shape of nanoparticle²¹.

Micheal addition reaction catalysed by transition metal ion has attracted much attention in recent years. This reaction can be catalysed by transition metals like ruthenium, cobalt, rhodium, iridium, nickel, palladium, platinum, silver and lanthanides like scandium, lanthanum, cerium, samarium and europium²². Micheal addition can be catalysed by organocatalyst like alkaloids, crown ethers and also by some organometallic catalysts. However, these catalysts are very costly and they require more reaction time. Therefore, it was planned in our present work to prepare superquality of cuprous oxide and Mn doped cuprous oxide nanoparticles.

In the present study, the synthesis of cuprous oxide nanoparticles has been reported by thermal decomposition method with the doping of 10% Mn^{2+} metal

ions. The synthesis of quasi sphere shaped Cu_2O with dopant Mn^{2+} has been carried out using oleic acid as a capping agent and octadecene as a solvent. Actually, the combination of capping agent oleic acid and oleyl amine was used for capping Cu_2O nanoparticle. The catalytic properties of the as-synthesized Cu_2O and Mn doped Cu_2O nanoparticles were evaluated in the Micheal addition reaction. This is the first report, where Mn doped Cu_2O nanoparticles have been used in Micheal addition reaction.

Results and discussion

XRD studies :

The XRD pattern of the as-synthesized sample is shown in Fig. 1. Fig. 1a is the XRD pattern of undoped Cu_2O NPs where, Fig. 1b is for 10% Mn ion doped Cu_2O NPs. Almost all peaks in the pattern could be indexed to a pure cubic cuprite phase Cu_2O . The peaks with 2θ value of 29.555° , 36.408° , 42.286° , 61.336° , 73.474° and 77.320° correspond to crystal plane of 110, 111, 200, 220, 311, 222, which is in good agreement with the literature (JCPDS File No. 5-0667). However, it is more important to note that the undoped

Fig. 1. XRD pattern of (a) Cu_2O NPs, (b) Mn doped (10%) Cu_2O NPs.

and doped samples have almost identical XRD patterns with an equal extent of peak broadening, suggesting these nanocrystals (NCs) have similar size and crystal structure independent of Mn^{2+} -doping. There are no other diffraction, which indicate high purity and crystalline nature of nanoparticles.

TEM analysis :

The size and morphology of the as-synthesized Mn doped Cu_2O and Cu_2O nanoparticles were analysed by transmission electron microscopy (TEM) measurements. The TEM images (Fig. 2) show that the Mn^{2+} doped (Fig. 2a and 2b) and undoped (Fig. 2c and 2d) Cu_2O nanoparticles consist of quasi spherical like structure. The diameter of quasi nanosphere was about 20–60 nm and length of about 100–200 nm. Oleyl amine is necessary to control morphology of nanocrystals²³. The crystallinity and crystallography of the product were also proven by ED (Fig. 3).

Fig. 2. TEM images of (a), (b) Cu_2O NPs doped with Mn ion (10%) and (c), (d) undoped Cu_2O NPs.

Fig. 3. ED pattern of Cu_2O NPs.

HR-SEM analysis :

Morphology of the product was also analyzed by HR-SEM. HR-SEM images (Fig. 4a and 4b) show the formation of quasi spherical shape of Cu₂O NPs. Fig. 4c shows quasi spherical shape to cubic shaped Mn doped (10%), Cu₂O NPs.

Fig. 4. HR-SEM image of (a), (b) undoped Cu₂O NPs and (c) Cu₂O NPs doped with 10% Mn.

Table 1. Percentage Mn (atomic wt%) as dopant in Cu₂O host determined by EDX

Sr. No.	Amount of Mn doped (at%) used in synthesis	Actual amount of Mn in Cu ₂ O matrix (from EDX) (%)
1.	0	–
2.	10	8.70

EDX analysis :

The weight percentage of Mn²⁺ was determined by Energy dispersive X-ray analysis (EDX) (Table 1 and Fig. 5). EDX analysis indicates that the well-cleaned final product is mostly composed of Cu and O, with no other signal (Fig. 5a). Fig. 5b is EDX images of Mn²⁺ doped Cu₂O NPs with 10% doping of Mn ion.

Micheal addition reaction :

Metal nanocatalyst can catalyze the Micheal addition reaction by acting as a Lewis acid²⁴. There are two important factors for the Micheal addition reac-

Fig. 5. EDX analysis of (a) undoped Cu₂O NPs and (b) 10% Mn doped Cu₂O NPs.

tion i.e. availability of compound containing active methylene group and α,β-unsaturated carbonyl compound. In the present case, chalcone was taken as a representative α,β-unsaturated carbonyl compound. This was treated with nitromethane. Addition reaction was carried out in the presence and absence of Cu₂O NPs. In this study, the catalytic efficiency of the Cu₂O and Mn doped Cu₂O NPs for Micheal addition was compared (Scheme 1). For this reaction, both; the catalyst and K₂CO₃ are essential and in absence of either, it leads to low yield and more reaction time (Tables 2 and 3). The most favourable reaction conditions for reaction are given in Table 2 (entry 9), which yields 97 ± 2% of product at 70 °C after 8 h.

Scheme 1

The process control of this reaction was done by TLC, where the product and reactant shows different spots. The reaction proceeds more rapidly (within 8 h) at 70 °C when sufficient quantities of catalyst and K₂CO₃ was used (Table 2, entry 9), whereas, in the absence of Cu₂O NPs, it requires 36 h (Table 2, entry 3).

Moreover, this reaction depends on the concentration of K₂CO₃. When the concentration of K₂CO₃ was increased in standard reaction, then yield of reaction was also increased (Table 2). Sufficient quantity of K₂CO₃ was required, because the low amount of K₂CO₃ caused an increase in the reaction time. The tempera-

Table 2. Micheal addition reaction using Cu₂O NPs

Sr. No.	Cu ₂ O (mg)	K ₂ CO ₃ (mol)	Temperature (°C)	Time (h)	Yield (%)
1.	None	–	30–35	–	–
2.	60	0.00	30–35	30	35
3.	None	0.0027	30–35	36	30
4.	60	0.0014	30–35	30	40
5.	60	0.002	30–35	20	50±3
6.	60	0.0025	30–35	15	97±2
7.	60	0.0027	30–35	12	96±2
8.	60	0.0030	60–70	9	97±2
9.	60	0.0030	70–80	8	96±2
10.	30	0.0030	30–35	18	96±2
11.	20	0.0030	30–35	19	96±2
12.	40	0.0030	30–35	18	96±2
13.	50	0.0030	30–35	15	96±2
14.	60	0.0030	30–35	12	96±2

ture was also an important factor in this reduction reaction. When the temperature was increased upto 70 °C, reaction was completed within 8 h of time and that too with high yield. This proves that as the reaction temperature increases, reaction time decreases (Table 2, entries 8 and 9).

Quantities of NPs play an important role in giving a high yield (Table 2, entries 6–9) under optimum reaction conditions. Though, minimum amount is sufficient for the reaction, it takes more time for completion (Table 2, entries 10–12).

When this reaction was carried out in the presence

Table 3. Micheal addition reaction using Mn doped Cu₂O NPs

Sr. No.	Mn doped Cu ₂ O (mg)	K ₂ CO ₃ (mol)	Temperature (°C)	Time (h)	Yield (%)
1.	None	–	30–35	–	–
2.	60	0.00	30–35	28	40
3.	None	0.0027	30–35	36	30
4.	60	0.0014	30–35	27	45
5.	60	0.002	30–35	17	50±3
6.	60	0.0025	30–35	15	97±2
7.	60	0.0027	30–35	12	97±2
8.	60	0.0030	60–70	8	97±2
9.	60	0.0030	70–80	7	96±2
10.	30	0.0030	30–35	16	96±2
11.	20	0.0030	30–35	17	96±2
12.	40	0.0030	30–35	16	96±2
13.	50	0.0030	30–35	13	96±2
14.	60	0.0030	30–35	12	96±2

of Mn doped (10%) Cu₂O NPs maintaining the rest of condition same, a decrease in reaction time was observed (Table 3). It was observed that doping increases the catalytic efficiency of nanoparticle²⁵. When Mn doped Cu₂O NPs was used as a catalyst in Micheal reaction, the time required for addition reaction was low as compared to previous reaction, where only Cu₂O NPs was used (Table 3).

Cu₂O and Mn doped Cu₂O NPs were used for Micheal addition of all substrates and they give more or less same yield in similar reaction time (Table 4).

Table 4. Comparison between Micheal addition reaction using Mn doped Cu₂O NPs and undoped Cu₂O NPs

Sr. No.	Reactant	Product	Time (h) (When catalyst Cu ₂ O used)	Time (h) (When catalyst Mn doped Cu ₂ O NPs used)	Yield (%)
1.	3-(Furan-2-yl)-1-phenylpropan-1-one	4-Acetyl-3-(furan-2-yl)-1-phenylhexane-1,5-dione	8.5	8	97±2
2.	3-(Benzo[d][1,3]dioxol-5-yl)-1-phenylpropan-1-one	4-Acetyl-3-(benzo[d][1,3]dioxol-5-yl)-1-phenylhexane-1,5-dione	9	7.5	96±2
3.	1-(4-Bromophenyl)-3-phenylpropan-1-one	4-Acetyl-1-(4-bromophenyl)-3-phenylhexane-1,5-dione	8	7	97±2
4.	1,3-Diphenylpropan-1-one	4-Acetyl-1,3-diphenylhexane-1,5-dione	9.5	8	97±2
5.	3-(4-Chlorophenyl)-1-phenylpropan-1-one	4-Acetyl-3-(4-chlorophenyl)-1-phenylhexane-1,5-dione	10	8.5	96±2

Experimental

Materials :

Cupric acetate, manganese acetate, trioctyl amine, oleic acid, oleyl amine and diacetone were purchased from Sigma Aldrich and used as such.

Synthesis of Mn^{2+} doped cuprous oxide (Cu_2O) nanoparticles :

In a typical synthesis, 2 g of cupric acetate was taken in 15 mL of octadecene and capping agent oleic acid (11 mL) was added. The reaction mixture was heated to desired temperature upto 160 °C with constant stirring. The mixture was kept at this temperature for 60 min. The mixture was gradually heated to 200 °C. Reaction mixture colour was changed to maroon. Immediately after colour change, the mixture was allowed to cool upto 170 °C. At this temperature, freshly prepared solution of manganese acetate in oleyl amine was added in reaction mixture. The mass was again heated upto 200 °C and the temperature was maintained for 30 min. This mass was allowed to cool at room temperature. Copper particles (Cu) were precipitated by addition of *n*-butanol. These particles were dispersed in hexane and gradually oxidised to form Mn doped Cu_2O nanoparticles. Colour of Cu_2O nanoparticles were red but in hexane, it formed a green colour solution. Mn doped Cu_2O nanoparticles were then centrifuged at 1000 rpm in ultracentrifuge machine and washed 2 times with ethanol followed by washing with acetone to remove any unreacted ions from mixture. To prepare undoped Cu_2O NPs, solution of manganese acetate in oleyl amine was not added after reaction mass was converted into maroon, keeping all other steps exactly the same as those for doped sample.

Characterization of Mn^{2+} doped Cu_2O nanoparticles :

X-Ray powder diffraction (XRD) was recorded on Shimadzu XRD 6000. Samples were prepared by pressing dried powder and patterns were collected with 2θ ranging from 0° to 80°. The morphology of nanoparticles was examined by transmission electron microscopy (TEM). TEM images were recorded on Philips CM 200 using an operating voltage of 200

KV. High resolution scanning electron microscopy was done on FEI Quanta, FEG 200 (HR-SEM). Elemental composition was determined by Energy dispersive X-ray (EDX) analysis of the vacuum dried doped and undoped Cu_2O nanoparticles by model-JSM-5610 LV attached to scanning electron microscopy (SEM) (Table 1). ICP-OES (Perkin-Elmer, 4300) was used to analyze the constituents present in traces. Micheal addition reactions catalyzed by doped and undoped Cu_2O nanoparticles were monitored by gas chromatography.

Micheal addition reaction :

In a typical reaction, chalcone (0.005 mol) was used as a starting material, nitromethane (0.0051) as a nucleophile, dichloromethane (10 mL) as solvent, Cu_2O NPs and Mn doped (10%) Cu_2O NPs as catalyst and K_2CO_3 as a base. All the raw materials were mixed together in 50 mL two neck round bottom flask and the reaction was carried out at 50 °C under stirring for 8 h in inert atmosphere.

The product was isolated by column chromatography (10 : 90, ethyl acetate in pet ether v/v) over silica (60–80 mesh). The spectroscopic data of this compound are similar with earlier reported. The reaction was also carried out in absence of Cu_2O NPs for comparison (Tables 2 and 3).

Micheal addition reaction of other compounds was carried out in a similar manner (Table 4). Micheal addition reaction monitoring was also done by thin-layer chromatography (TLC). The products purified by column chromatography in pet ether were analyzed by GC.

Conclusion

Mn^{2+} doped Cu_2O nanoparticles have been successfully synthesized using a thermal decomposition method. The TEM study revealed that quasi sphere shape NPs were obtained, when combination of capping agent like oleic acid and oleyl amine were used. The present study allowed us to conclude that Cu_2O NPs can be used for the Micheal addition of nitrocompounds. Further, doping Cu_2O NPs with Mn^{2+} also helped in increasing the catalytic efficiency of Cu_2O NPs.

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